

TYPES OF INTERNATIONAL WORDS AND THEIR LEXICOGRAPHICAL INTERPRETATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to the classification of English borrowings into Uzbek. It also deals with lexicographic analysis of International words in two languages. The author reveals the concept of International words and considers its wide range of usage in modern linguistics. The article provides a brief overview of International words classification and gives clear examples for lexicographical interpretation.*

Key words: *International words, borrowed words, neologisms, lexicography, vocabulary, word formation.*

Introduction

The rise of mass media, particularly the Internet, has led in a huge increase in worldwide vocabulary. All languages are influenced by the cultural and social environment in which they operate, and vocabulary reflects diverse cross-national contacts. International terms are used extensively in a wide range of terminological systems, including science, industry, technology and art language. The etymological sources for this vocabulary show the evolution of world civilization.

Methods

In this work method of comparative lexicographical analysis is used.

Literature review

As the vocabulary of a language evolves in response to changes in society, the role of international words in the enrichment of vocabulary plays a primary role. After independence, the direct acquisition of international words into our language will increase. In particular, English borrowings play an important role in Uzbek word stock. Many of these words are now actively used in spoken and written speech as modern

layering vocabulary. English borrowings can be classified according to the following thematic groups:

1. International words of thematic groups in the socio-political sphere;
2. International words of thematic groups related to the economic sphere;
3. International words of thematic groups in the field of culture and education;
4. International words of thematic group on sports.

The International words of the thematic group on socio-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports can be classified on the basis of internal divisions as followings:

International words of thematic groups in the socio-political sphere	International words of thematic groups related to the economic sphere	International words of thematic groups in the field of culture and education	International words of thematic group on sports
Worldview, theory and socio-political terms: formalism, centrism, trade unionism, impeachment, lockout, summit, Labor, boycott	Economic sphere and trade: leasing, export, banknote, voucher, dealer, discount, import, investor, barter, budget, marketing, businessmen,	Fields of science, names of directions: logistics, ufology, management, etc.	Sports: badminton, basketball, knockdownstart, time-out, tennis, finish, football, hockey, championship, volleyball bodybuilding, etc.
Social class: like a lord, a farmer	Food names: steak, hamburger, yogurt, cake,	Related to physics and radio engineering:	

	ketchup, jam, etc.	wattmeter, dielectric, neutron, radar, speedometer, transistor, reactor, etc.	
Ethnographic term: totem, totemism, etc.	Drink names: cocktail, coca-cola, pepsicola, pom, whiskey, etc.	In the field of medicine: catgut, shock, hemorrhoids, tracheitis, quinine, gutta-percha, stress, drainage, etc.	
Meeting names: such as briefings.	Clothing names: jumper, jeans, cowboy, jacket, pyjamas, sweater, panties, reglan	Types of puzzles in periodicals: crossword, chainword.	
Terrorism and sabotage: like gangsters,	Names of household items: mixer, player, water dispenser,	Printing (publishing): press conference, press secretary,	

	wifi, coffee maker etc	printer, print, copy, etc.	
Name of official normative-technical document: as standard. (In England and America) For men, a word that is usually used in front of a name or surname: like a mister.	Currency names: dollar, cent, shilling, pound sterling, etc. Unit of measure: like a barrel.	In the field of information technology: telegraph display, printer, monitor, multimedia, scanner, CD, ticket, internet, site, paging, hacker, file, floppy disk,	

Furthermore :

Cosmetics: make-up, shampoo, gel, hair dryer, spa service, etc.

Location names: railway station, drainage, square, camping, club, college, cottage, motel, bar (small restaurant, tavern), tunnel, zoo, hall, park, supermarket, etc.

Name of vehicles: trolleybus, express train, tram, pickup, liner, trailer, tanker, etc.

Scientific terminology:

Technical names: terminal, truck, antifreeze, auto rally, vulcanization, blooming, cracking, scraper, timer, injector, laser, server, gin, block, bulldozer, wagon, excavator, combine, magneto, starter , stop-crane, crankcase, buffer, nipple, etc.

Related to physics and radio engineering: wattmeter, dielectric, neutron, radar, speedometer, transistor, reactor, etc.

Biology, botany, physiology, geography: clone, mimicry, wilt, dendropark, iceberg.

Chemicals: phosphorite, potash, alcohol, coke, compost, lewisite, toner, formalin, phosphates, furfural, dust, reagent, reactor, etc.

Zoology: bulldog, gorilla, gibbon, kangaroo, broiler, etc.

Drug names: such as doping.

Fuel names: like kerosene.

Chemically elastic substance: such as rubber.

In the field of construction: elevators, escalators, etc.

Among the English lexemes, the ones related to household and trade names also play an important role in Uzbek lexicon and the supermarket lexeme has lost its neologism version and moved to the modern layer vocabulary. There are shop, mini-market, supermarket, hypermarket, megamarket, shopping mall (Moll. "Mall" alley) in the Trade names, and the hypermarket lexeme has a neologism character. Megamarket and mall lexemes are typical of Russian lexicon and have not been mastered in Uzbek yet.

As the use of English borrowings in our language becomes more active, the etymological history of some words related to lexical meaning is also of interest to linguists. For example, a cowboy [visual. cow-boy <cow - sigir + boy - yigit] in the Western United States; it does not seem unnatural to express the meaning of a brave, courageous young man. A word Hot-dog, a delicious and light meal for young people, also acquired in our language after independence. [hot - issiq; and dog - it] raises the suspicion that even a person with a basic knowledge of English may have the name of a dish made from dog meat. However, the etymology of food names, which have such a history, requires a large amount of explanation. Hot dogs were used on websites in 1884 as a synonym for sausage, and the motto of the sausage makers at the time was "Love me, love my dog," meaning to throw a bone at a dog if you respect the owner. It is said to have been mentioned first by Berry Popik, and in 1906 recognized by the famous cartoonist Thomas Aloysius Dorgan. There are other versions of the etymology of the word 'hot dog'. In short, the hot dog does not have any dog meat at all, but only beef or chicken. The cocktail lexeme also has its own etymological history in the English that means cocktail – xo'rozning dumi. In addition, makintosh [eng. Mackintosh] on behalf of the Scottish chemist Mackintosh, who invented the waterproof fabric; rugby used in sports on behalf of the English rugby town; badminton [eng. Badminton] on behalf of the city of Badminton in England; reglan [eng. Reglan] on behalf

of the British General Reglan; sheviot [eng. Cheviot] On behalf of the Cheviot Hills, a breed of fine-wool sheep in Scotland; boycott representing political understanding [visual. The lexeme Boycott] is derived from the name of a large English landowner, Ch.K. Boycott can be understood as an extension of the meaning of proper names.

In general, the names of food products, beverages, clothes, household items, organizations, locations, vehicles, drugs, fuel products, which are available in our lexicon, serve to fill the gaps in some thematic groups in the Uzbek vocabulary.

In addition to being polysemantic, changes that occurred in the semantics of English borrowings in our word stock take a leading position in the process of language phenomena, such as the expansion of the meaning of words and their active participation in the formation of Uzbek words.

It is known that among Uzbek lexemes borrowed from English, -er, -ing, -ment, -tion, -men, -time, -show, (show-), are more noticeable. To illustrate, blogger, management, marketing, tuition, businessmen, like time, talk show, etc.

In conclusion, the old edition of the Uzbek dictionary contains about 80 English borrowings, while the new edition contains more than 500 words. There are also more than 350 words in the "Explanatory Dictionary of English words in the Uzbek language", as well as neologisms used in the periodicals, "English-Uzbek-Russian information technology" and the Internet. It is safe to say that more than a thousand lexemes have been borrowed in our language at the expense of English.

It can be seen that some of International words borrowed from English that are actively used in our everyday speech are not included in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language". For example, many words such as image, Coca-Cola, mini-market, hypermarket, cheeseburger, hot dog, chips, netbook, bluetooth, flash memory, Wi-Fi, tablet, intranet should be included in our dictionary system.

International words from English can be divided into socio-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports thematic groups in our language. The number of English-speaking subjects in the field of sports has increased so much since independence that is convenient and appropriate to study them systematically in Uzbek language.

REFERENCES:

1. Chwegler Armin Language and Globalization. University of California, Irvine, 2006
2. Тарасова Л.А. Интернациональная лексика как частный случай заимствований.
3. Mahmudov N. O'zbek tilida baynalminal so'zlar: me'yor va milliylik // O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. 2010. -№ 6.
4. Словарь иностранных слов.- Комлев Н.Г.,2006
5. <http://www.globalization101.org/uploads/File/Syllabus-Lang-Globalization.pdf>
6. <https://studfile.net/>